

1. UNIVERSITY-WIDE RESEARCH GRANTS FOR LIBRARIANS

COVER SHEET

NOTE: Grant proposals are confidential until funding decisions are made.

INSTRUCTIONS: The applicant(s) must submit two (2) copies of their application packet. The application packet consists of the Cover Sheet and the Proposal. Applicants send 1 (one) printed copy of their application packet, with signatures, to the Chair of the divisional research committee, who forwards the packet to the Chair of the university-wide Research and Professional Development Committee. Applicants send the second copy of their application packet as an email attachment to the Chair of the divisional research committee who forwards it on to the Chair of the university-wide Research and Professional Development Committee.

Date of Application: October 18, 2016
Title of Proposal/Project: DResSUP for Librarians
Expected Length of Project : January 9, 2017-October 31, 2017 (10 months)
Total Funds Requested from LAUC University-Wide Research Funds: \$5,000
Primary Applicant Your Name (include your signature on the paper copy): Zoe Borovsky Academic Rank and Working Title: Librarian (Librarian for Digital Research and Scholarship) Bargaining Unit Member/Non-Member: Member Campus Surface Mail Address: Collections, Research & Instructional Services, AA1540J YRL, MC: 157511 Telephone and Email Address: 310-825-4954 zoe@library.ucla.edu URL for home campus directory (will be used for link on LAUC University-Wide

Funded Research Grants web page): <https://www.library.ucla.edu/support/research-help/digital-research-start-partnerships-graduate-students-dressup>

Co-Applicant(s)

Name: Pete Broadwell

Academic Rank and Working Title: Programmer Analyst III (Academic Projects Developer)

Bargaining Unit Member/Non-Member: Non-Member

Campus Surface Mail Address: Digital Library Program, 22484 YRL MC: 157511

Telephone and Email Address: 310-825-6158 broadwell@library.ucla.edu

Co-Applicant(s)

Name: Dawn Childress

Academic Rank and Working Title: Associate Librarian (Digital Collections and Scholarship)

Bargaining Unit Member/Non-Member: Member

Campus Surface Mail Address: Digital Library Program, 22484 YRL, MC: 157511

Telephone and Email Address: 310-794-5849 dchildress@library.ucla.edu

Co-Applicant(s)

Name: Claudia Horning

Academic Rank and Working Title: Associate Librarian (Director, Metadata Services)

Bargaining Unit Member/Non-Member: Member

Campus Surface Mail Address: Cataloging & Metadata Center, 11020 Kinross Ave, MC: 723011

Telephone and Email Address: 310-825-4092 chorning@library.ucla.edu

Co-Applicant(s)

Name: Andy Rutkowski

Academic Rank and Working Title: Associate Librarian (Geospatial Librarian)

Bargaining Unit Member/Non-Member: Member

Campus Surface Mail Address: Collections, Research & Instructional Services/Digital Library Program, A1540 YRL, MC: 157511

Telephone and Email Address: 310-267-5599 arutkowski@library.ucla.edu

Proposal Abstract (not to exceed 250 words):

The UCLA Library's Core DResSUP team (Borovsky, Broadwell, Childress, Horning, and Rutkowski) proposes to teach a continuing education program for librarians that gradually integrates them into a program we developed for UCLA graduate students. DResSUP stands for Digital Research StartUp

Partnerships. Our proposal is designed to prepare librarians as active partners in the digital research process by introducing them to tools and methods that are increasingly important to advanced research. Our proposal builds capacity in the library for supporting digital research in a way that is sustainable over the long term. We envision that librarians we train will become members of our dynamic, cross-unit team, working with us to support digital research. The training program will take a project-based approach, building skills while working on a digital research project related to the LA Times Photographic Archive. The research for this proposal tests whether this approach is an effective way for librarians to develop the skills that allow them to effectively engage with digital researchers. In addition, librarian partners will assist with teaching workshops, thus gaining pedagogical skills they can immediately put to use in their work. Finally, these librarians will be working on a team-based digital research project that they can publish online and present to their colleagues. Based on the assessments that we will conduct as part of this proposal, we plan to submit an IMLS grant proposal to further expand the project to more graduate students as well as librarians.

Does the proposal require any of the following:

Use of UC Library facilities or other site(s) requiring prior approval (Yes/No): No

If yes, include signature and position of person authorized to permit use of facilities on paper copy of application:

Release time (Yes/No): Yes

If yes, include signature(s) of person(s) authorized to approve release time on paper copy of application: Susan Parker, Deputy University Librarian, UCLA.

Use of Human Subjects (Yes/No): No

If yes, attach appropriate university form to paper application form. The process of obtaining IRB approval or a determination of exemption from subject protection regulations does not have to be completed prior to submitting your grant proposal.

However, the grant cannot be awarded without evidence that the approval or exemption has been obtained.

List any previous grant proposals (divisional and university-wide) from this program that have been awarded to the primary applicant or co-applicants by title. Include date of completion and amount funded: Allison Benedetti (Co-applicants: Marta Brunner, Jennifer Osorio, Zoe Borovsky), "North Campus Research Community Study: An Assessment of Needs and Practices" (2013-14), in progress, \$9,708.80.

Budget Summary

Total amount requested from LAUC statewide research funds: \$5,000

Total amount requested from LAUC divisional research funds: 0

Other funding obtained or expected (amount and source): 0

Fiscal Year of Application (fiscal year that funding begins): 2016/2017

New Project (Yes/No): Yes

Supplemental Funding (Yes/No): No (UCLA Library funding will be used to purchase MacBook Pros, and software. See Budget.)

Salaries: \$5,000

Total Salaries: \$5,000

Supplies: 0

Total Supplies: 0

Travel: 0

Total Travel: 0

Other Expenses: 0

Total Other Expenses: 0

Total State-Wide Research Funds Requested: \$5,000

Revised 9/2006 bhg

2. Need for Research

Increasingly, humanities scholars (and scholars in humanistic social sciences) recognize the value of digital research tools and methods such as text mining and spatial analysis. As more content is digitized, these methods are becoming more useful, especially to graduate students who are at a formative stage in their careers. Librarians and library staff are keen to support these researchers and meet these increasing demands. To meet the needs of graduate students, UCLA librarians developed DResSUP, a six-week summer program designed as partnerships between library staff and researchers.¹ At UCLA Libraries, only a handful of us have the expertise to engage with these users beyond the initial phase of data discovery. Some of our colleagues would like to participate but they express concerns about their lack of familiarity with increasingly complex tools and methods. They recognize that they face a steep learning curve, one that will require additional resources to surmount. We propose to extend our program to develop partnerships with librarians motivated to learn these skills.

UCLA Library is not alone in experimenting with ways to build capacity for digital research. In a 2012 ARL Fall Forum report, Cawthorne, Lewis and Wang maintained that all the libraries they interviewed identified a scarcity of vacant or new positions that could be defined in ways that would meet these new demands.² Jaguszewski and Williams identified two strategies to address this shortage: 1) short-term hiring practices, non-permanent hires. 2) invest in strong and well-planned staff development.³ UCLA has pursued both strategies. In the short-term, we have hosted CLIR fellows. One of these CLIR fellows, Peter Broadwell, has become a permanent addition to library staff and a core member of our DResSUP team. Along the lines of the second suggestion, UCLA Library has hired functional experts in GIS (Rutkowski), Digital Library/Scholarship (Childress), and hybrid subject/functional experts in Digital Humanities (Borovsky). With new interdisciplinary programs emerging at UCLA (e.g. Digital Humanities and Urban Humanities) our small team, although expanding, is divided and stretched to its limit providing support for digital projects in courses as well as research undertaken by individual scholars and teams. This proposal addresses the need for well-planned staff development to meet these growing demands by building capacity and programs that are sustainable and scalable over the long-term.

¹ We emphasize in our DResSUP promotional materials, that our graduate student “partnerships” are not traditional paid fellowships. Graduate student partners receive support through their participation.

² Jon E. Cawthorne, Vivian Lewis, and Xuemao Wang, “Transforming the Research Library Workforce: A Scenarios Approach” (ARL Fall Forum, Washington, D.C., October 11, 2012), <http://www.arl.org/storage/documents/publications/ff12-cawthorne-lewis-wang.pdf> .

³ Janice M. Jaguszewski and Karen Williams, “Transforming Liaison Roles in Research Libraries” (Association of Research Libraries, 2013).

+ Preparing for the Future: Retraining & Retooling

- Streamline current workflow. Eliminate routine work wherever possible. Free up existing capacity and repurpose them.
- Get staff out of the library (“see and be seen” on campus)
- Offer rich training & development opportunities as broadly as possible.
 - Cultivate your “stars” selectively (offer deep opportunities to those who are the most receptive).
- Embed librarians in research teams now (even small projects).
- Cultivate data management / digital scholarship skills now.

Slide from Cawthorne, et al. 2012 ARL presentation, “Transforming the Research Library Workforce.”

The UCLA Library has supported graduate students doing digital research projects through a summer pilot program called DResSUP (Digital Research Start-Up Partnerships). The program has run successfully for six weeks

during the past two summers (2015 and 2016). The goal of DResSUP is to engage librarians with researchers during the process of moving from digital collection-building to analysis to publication, partnering with scholars as they navigate the various types of expertise needed during the research process. Our core team includes four library staff members: Zoe Borovsky, Peter Broadwell, Dawn Childress, Claudia Horning, Andy Rutkowski; as well as a faculty advisor, Jonathan Crisman (Urban Humanities).

UCLA librarians propose to establish a continuing education program for librarians by building upon and extending the DResSUP incubator model. This proposal tests our hypothesis that, in addition to resources, librarians embarking upon this type of development will also need motivation and support during the initial skill-building phase, when these newly-acquired skills may not yet be sufficient for them to be embedded as the sole librarian in a research team. Our proposal builds programmatically towards the embedding process. During their first year of training,⁴ “partner” librarians entering the DResSUP program will engage with researchers as members of an established “community of practice”, one in which core library staff function as mentors. Core staff have already been teaching and learning along with graduate student researchers who participate in the DResSUP program during the summer.⁵ We expect that using core staff as models of this team-based, highly collaborative approach will alleviate

⁴ We plan to submit an IMLS grant expanding DResSUP for Librarians to a two-year training cycle. The second year would be a formal mentoring program, when partner librarians would become “core” members of DResSUP.

⁵ Feedback from DResSUP graduate student partners emphasized how much they appreciated working with staff who were willing to explore and learn new tools along with them. One student wrote: “[w]hen I have done other things such as this the people running the program tend to want to fit your idea into what they already know and would rather you make the changes than try to learn along with you about how you can accomplish your own vision.”

much of the resistance towards (and anxieties around) notions of “retooling” and “reskilling” that continuing education programs tend to evoke among more experienced and highly skilled librarians.

Finally, we believe that taking a project-based approach, incorporating skill-building while working on a digital research project, will help sustain motivation and allow librarians to connect the training with projects relevant to areas of ongoing research within the library and in communities of scholars in Los Angeles. We have chosen the rich and extensive Los Angeles Times Photographic Archive, a cornerstone of UCLA’s Digital Library Collections and the Collecting LA initiative, as a central source of materials around which partner librarians can build their own digital research projects.⁶

To support this work, University Librarian Virginia Steel has, for the past two summers, provided generous funding that allowed us to hire one or two graduate student assistant(s) to work on four or five graduate student projects each summer. Although the DResSUP program is considered a great success, we realize that, in order for it to become scalable and sustainable, we must build capacity and offer the program to more students. Rather than hiring short-term assistants, we propose to build upon the enthusiasm and interest the program has generated among our colleagues. Taking inspiration from the Developing Librarian program at Columbia (<https://devlib.library.columbia.edu/about/>), we propose to move one step further: during the summer, the librarian “partner” track and the graduate student “partner” track for DResSUP will become integrated. Librarian partners will 1) assist core staff members as they teach workshops, and 2) work on their own digital research project as the graduate student partners work on their own projects. We expect that, by the end of the summer, partner librarians will be ready to take on roles as instructors as they continue to learn and develop skills alongside the graduate student partners.

University Librarian Virginia Steel has written a letter of support for this proposal (Appendix D), to indicate her support for providing release time for three of the “partner” librarians who will be trained, the MacBook Pros that they will use, and an additional graduate student assistant working full-time during the summer program.

3. Design and Methodology

DResSUP for Librarians would begin during the academic year and focus on the Collecting Los Angeles theme. We propose a pilot program with funding from LAUC and the UCLA Library to establish the first year of the training program. In the Fall Quarter, DResSUP core staff will issue a call for applicants and select three librarians and form a cohort during Winter Quarter. Ideally, the goal is to have librarians

⁶ Our DResSUP logo features an amusing photograph from this collection, of the author Lawrence Lipton, chronicler of the LA beatnik scene. Lipton is pictured demonstrating his robot, DUHAB, (detector of undesirable habitués). During a contentious and protracted debate with local police and property owners, Lipton claimed that DUHAB would keep the riff-raff-raff out of the infamous beatnik hangout (the “Gas House”) in Venice Beach. UCLA Library has Lawrence Lipton’s papers: <http://www.oac.cdlib.org/findaid/ark:/13030/ft0r29n6qr/>

representing a variety of disciplinary areas.⁷ These “partner” librarians will join DResSUP core staff and work together to conceptualize, build, and present (in Fall 2017) a digital research project based on the Los Angeles Times Photographic Archive.⁸ Much of this collection has already been digitized and made available through UCLA’s Digital Library Collections.

These three partner librarians will, in the Winter Quarter, obtain *four hours per week release time for ten weeks* from their regular duties to engage in DResSUP activities. DResSUP core staff will, using LAUC funding, hire a part-time graduate student assistant to work during Winter and Spring Quarters with the partner librarians. Each partner librarian will receive a new (MacBook Pro) laptop and software, the same dual-book platform made available for check-out by students in most UCLA Libraries. The laptops will allow partner

librarians to participate in digital research workshops (taught by the core DResSUP library staff members) designed to develop hands-on, practical skills as they work through the phases of the digital research lifecycle: 1) finding and/or **collecting** data, 2) processing, **cleaning** and organizing data, 3) **analyzing** and visualizing data, and, finally, 4) **sharing** and publishing data.

Research data life-cycle

⁷ We would aim for one librarian from each of three divisions: Humanities & Social Sciences, Arts and Music, and Sciences.

⁸ The finding aid for this collection is at: <http://www.oac.cdlib.org/findaid/ark:/13030/kt7489n8x1/>

In the Spring Quarter, librarians will have release time up to *eight hours per week for nine weeks*. Having already participated in workshops during the Winter Quarter, they will, in this quarter, assist with the workshops. *They will be released 50% time for one week* when they will work together to plan a digital research project related to “Collecting LA”. This project plan will then become the basis for a project they can submit as their group’s proposal to the DResSUP summer program. In addition, they will participate in discussions about project-based learning and methodologies. When DResSUP for graduate students begin in the summer, the *librarian partners will be released 50%-time for seven weeks*.

In addition to producing an online digital research project with these partner librarians, we will test the efficacy of integrating librarian continuing education/training with a partnership program designed for the researchers they seek to support. Feedback from the graduate students these last two years emphasized how much they appreciated that DResSUP staff members were learning along with them, rather than teaching only the tools and techniques we had already mastered. Having already established a small “learning community,” and having seen the benefits of being more connected to each other and researchers, we seek funding to extend that community by including our colleagues. We will assess the effectiveness of the program by asking partner librarians to write reflective essays at the beginning and the end of the program. We will conduct one focus group at the end of the program asking partners to compare those essays and reflect on what worked well and what could be improved. We expect that after a year of this program, librarians will have developed the methodological, pedagogical, technical, and communication skills so that they can engage meaningfully with faculty and graduate student researchers.

However, we also expect that the full development of these skills will depend on the partner librarians’ pre-existing skill levels, an ongoing commitment to their own professional development, and opportunities to practice their skills by engaging productively with researchers on an ongoing basis.

4. Budget

The bulk of the budget for this proposal comes from the UCLA Library itself. Our Letter of Support from University Librarian Virginia Steel outlines the support the library is willing to contribute: laptops, software, release time for both the librarian cohort (and the core DResSUP team) as well as funding for one full-time graduate student for seven weeks during the summer.

Funding from LAUC would be used to hire the graduate student assistant working part-time during Winter and Spring Quarters. We are requesting \$5,000 (of \$6,828) in order to pay the Winter and Spring student assistant a part-time salary (20 hours per week for 20 weeks at \$17.07/hour). This hourly rate is consistent with what we have paid in the past to hire a student with technical skills that would complement and augment the skills of the core DResSUP team. Because we have had several highly-

qualified graduate students apply to the DResSUP program these past two years, we are confident that we will be able to hire excellent candidates.⁹

Item	Calculation	Total amount	LAUC portion	UCLA portion
1 graduate student assistant II, 20 hrs. per week, 2 quarters: Winter and Spring.	20 hours x 20 weeks at \$17.07 per hour	\$6,828	\$5,000	\$1,828
Benefits for grad student assistant (2 quarters)	5% of \$6,828	\$342		\$342
3-15" MacBook Pro w/1TB SSD and warranty	3 x \$3,260	\$9,780		\$9,780
Software: Adobe Creative Cloud (\$140 per year), Parallel Desktop (\$45 per year to run Windows)	3 x \$185	\$555		\$555
Totals		\$17,505	\$5,000	\$12,505

5. Supplemental Budget Sheet (N/A)

6. Personnel (CVs follow Appendix D, pages 34-44)

I. Zoe Borovsky, Ph.D.

Librarian, Librarian for Digital Research and Scholarship, Charles E. Young Research Library. Project Lead for DResSUP. Supervises the graduate student assistant.

⁹ The hourly wage for DResSUP graduate student assistants have been \$17.07 per hour for summer 2015 and 2016. UCLA will pay the 5% benefits for the student position. See Appendix B for the official job description for this position.

II. Peter Broadwell, Ph.D.

Programmer Analyst III, Academic Projects Developer, Digital Library Program. Assists in recruitment of librarian partners, graduate student helpers, and summer graduate student participants. Leads or assists with occasional workshops and tutorials on digital research technologies of interest to the participants.

III. Dawn Childress

Librarian, Digital Collections & Scholarship, Digital Library Program. Assists in recruitment of librarian partners, graduate student helpers, and summer graduate student participants. Leads or assists with occasional workshops and tutorials on digital research technologies of interest to the participants.

IV. Claudia Horning

Director, Metadata Services, Cataloging & Metadata Center. Assists in recruitment of librarian partners, graduate student helpers, and summer graduate student participants. Leads or assists with occasional workshops and tutorials on digital research technologies of interest to the participants.

V. Andy Rutkowski

Associate Librarian, Geospatial Librarian, Charles E. Young Research Library. Assists in recruitment of librarian partners, graduate student helpers, and summer graduate student participants. Leads or assists with occasional workshops and tutorials on digital research technologies of interest to the participants.

7. Timetable for Completion

Fall Quarter, 2017 (Before LAUC grant-funded Work Begins)

Core DResSUP staff members will set the schedule for Winter and Spring, recruit and select three partner librarians and begin recruiting one part-time graduate student assistant. The partner librarians will work with their supervisors and peers to arrange schedules to accommodate release time during Winter, Spring, and Summer.

Winter Quarter, 2017

DResSUP for Librarians would begin January 9, 2017, with internal library workshops, taught by core DResSUP librarians, about the research data lifecycle. However, rather than focusing on individual tools and methods, we will work together on a project that uses digital library data to create an interactive website. By taking a project-based approach, the teaching and learning of both practical tools and theoretical methods is integrated with work on the project itself.

The research data life-cycle, as we present it in DResSUP (Collect, Clean, Analyze, and Share) is an iterative process. We will teach partner librarians to create a small, sample dataset from raw data that they run through the first (four-phase) cycle. After ironing out the issues, they repeat the cycle again. Only after they are able to successfully complete the entire cycle using a small, sample dataset do they scale up to using a larger set (or subset) of data.

Week 1: (Jan 9, 2017). The graduate student assistant will begin working part-time for the DResSUP program and based in the Scholarly Innovation Lab (SIL) located in the Research Commons of the Charles

E. Young Library.¹⁰ S/he will be supervised by Zoe Borovsky. Zoe will ensure that the graduate student assistant's time is focused primarily on facilitating the work of the librarian partners. Zoe will arrange for the graduate student assistant to meet with the core DResSUP team, previous graduate student assistants and partners, and perform a review of materials and assessments from the previous summer's program.

Week 2: After an introduction to the program, partner librarians will write a self-assessment of the digital research skills, recognizing that these are areas the program is designed to enhance. Partner librarians will address their preparedness to

- 1) Support basic digital research questions.
- 2) Identify the research question(s) and methods underlying digital research projects.
- 3) Articulate the goal of their digital research project: the research question(s) at the core of the project.
- 4) Describe each phase of the digital research process and their role(s) in the project.
- 5) Be conversant in project-based learning and methodology.
- 6) Understand how research teams function.
- 7) Participate in designing a project-based workshop or tutorial.
- 8) Have a basic understanding of project management.
- 9) Describe how digital research projects, tools and/or methods can be viewed as an extension of librarianship and become part of the scholarly record.
- 10) Define a role (or roles) they are ready to play in support of digital scholarship in the UCLA Library and the UCLA Community.
- 11) Articulate next steps in the development of their own digital research skills, teaching and research.

Week 3: Training sessions will begin (Jan 23, 2017). Partner librarians will receive their MacBook Pro laptops and use them for their regular duties as well as training sessions. The partners, core staff and the graduate student assistant will meet twice a week for two hours 1) once for an instructor-led workshop, and 2) the second session will either be a one-hour presentation by a previous DResSUP graduate student partner followed by informal discussion, or facilitated hands-on project time with the graduate student assistant and/or a core DResSUP staff member.¹¹

We estimate that partner librarians will need release time, up to a *maximum of four hours per week (for ten weeks)* to participate in the workshops, read background literature, and take (selected) self-directed tutorials. The graduate student assistant will work in the Scholarly Innovation Lab (SIL) of the Research

¹⁰ The Scholarly Innovation Lab is a joint project between UCLA Library's Center for Digital Humanities and the UCLA Library. See: <http://www.library.ucla.edu/yrl/scholarly-innovation-lab-sil>. The SIL has been the "home-base" for the DResSUP program where students and staff work together.

¹¹ These sessions will be open to all UCLA librarians who wish to participate, but the primary audience will be the DResSUP partner librarians.

Commons and be available to assist partner librarians. We will use digitized images and metadata from the Los Angeles Times Photo Archive as our training data set for all workshops.

Week 4 (begins Jan 30, 2017): **Collection:** Finding published data sets, using web-scraping tools (Import.io), and/or collecting your own data (surveys, interviews). Create a project plan. Instructor: Zoe Borovsky and Peter Broadwell. Readings on project-based learning and project management.

Week 5 (begins Feb 6): **Cleaning, Pre-processing:** Beginning with a “raw” set of data, work through the (pre-defined) steps of cleaning the data using [OpenRefine](#) software. Learn to use regular expressions. Geo-code using ArcGIS to add latitude and longitude. Instructors: Dawn Childress and Andy Rutkowski.

A screenshot of three visualizations of the same dataset, LA Dance Clubs, created during a DResSUP workshop by students using data scraped from Yelp.com, geo-coded in Google Fusion Tables and Google Earth, and then visualized using Tableau Public software.

Week 6 (begins Feb 13): **Analysis, Visualization:** Perform a spatial analysis in [Tableau Public](#) using the mapping function. Add timeline functionality to view spatial changes over time. Explore the data set, and create two other visualizations. Instructors: Andy Rutkowski and Zoe Borovsky. Readings on mapping, visualization.

Week 7 (begins Feb 20): **Sharing, Publishing:** Publish interactive time-map using Tableau Public’s story-points function. Annotate the time-map providing links back to each item in UCLA’s Digital Library Collection. Using the same data, create another visualization in a similar platform, such as Library of Congress’s [ViewShare](#). Compare the two platforms in terms of ease of use, flexibility, functionality. Discuss ways of publishing the augmented data set. Instructors: Claudia Horning and Dawn Childress.

Week 8 (begins Feb. 27): Core DResSUP staff will:

- 1) Prepare a letter of intent for a Laura Bush 21st Century Librarian Program¹² to expand DResSUP into a two-year continuing education training program for librarians.¹³

¹²Information about this grant is here: <https://www.ims.gov/nofo/laura-bush-21st-century-librarian-program-fy17-notice-funding-opportunity>

¹³ We envision a third track of DResSUP designed to facilitate faculty research projects. This track will extend DResSUP to incorporate a training program for Graduate Student Research Assistants. The library will train

2) Prepare for a text/data mining joint session with DResSUP librarians, previous graduate student partners and the UCLA Library's Scholarly Communications Team.

Week 9 (begins March 6). Joint text/data mining session: DResSUP and UCLA Library's Scholarly Communications Team. This session will focus on designing workflows to resolve licensing issues researchers encounter when requesting text/data mining access to library resources and/or acquisition of text/data resources for text/data mining projects.

Spring Quarter, 2017

Core (and partner) DResSUP staff will offer the same workshop series above, but these workshops will be open to the larger UCLA community. The workshops will provide an opportunity to begin recruiting graduate students for the Summer DResSUP program.

Partner librarians and the graduate student assistant will

- 1) Create promotional materials for the workshops and a strategy for outreach.
- 2) Prepare instructional materials, data sets, exercises, background readings, additional tutorials for the workshops.
- 3) Attend and assist with the workshops.
- 4) Conceptualize, plan, and research their summer DResSUP project.

We expect partner librarians will need release time for up to a maximum of *eight hours per week for nine weeks* in order to fully participate in the program.

In addition, we estimate that having one week of 50% release time (for one week: Week 8) for partner librarians to focus together on project planning would be time well-spent. During this week, core staff will arrange a daily "office hour" to answer questions and brainstorm ideas.¹⁴

At the end of the quarter, partner librarians should have a draft of a project plan (or plans) they can submit as part of the DResSUP application cycle.

Core staff will

- 1) Provide logistical support for DResSUP Summer 2017, including recruitment, publicity, application process and partner application review.
- 2) Recruit and hire the graduate student assistant for the Summer, and
- 3) Create the syllabus (with teaching assignments) for the seven-week DResSUP program.
- 4) Draft the application and prepare selected sections of an IMLS grant, due September 1, 2017.
- 5) Prepare the LAUC status report, due April 14, 2017.

Summer, 2017

We plan to begin the summer DResSUP program on July 17 with a full-day Boot Camp. The program runs for seven weeks ending on Aug 25. The first three weeks (July 17-Aug 5) focus on the research life-

graduate student researchers who will then form a pool of experts from which UCLA faculty can hire using their Academic Senate Research Grant funds.

¹⁴ Deputy University Librarian Susan Parker has signed the Cover Sheet form and agreed to provide the release time for the partner librarians. Because we have not yet selected the partner librarians, DUL Parker's signature and Virginia Steel's letter indicates UCLA Library's willingness to provide release time.

cycle workshops: Collection, Cleaning, and Analysis. We expect that, having participated in these workshops during Winter and Spring, the librarian/partner cohort will be able to co-lead the summer workshops with core DResSUP staff. Librarian partners will have *50% release-time during the seven-week program*.

Weeks 1-6: See Appendix A for Curriculum from Summer 2016.

Week 7: Librarian partners will write a self-assessment addressing the same areas as they did at the beginning of the program. Then core library staff will organize a focus group, asking partner librarians to compare their initial and final assessments and reflect on the effectiveness of the program. The session will be recorded so that extracts can be used during the preparation of our final report.

Partner librarians will then prepare for an all-staff library presentation of their project in the Fall. Core DResSUP staff will prepare an internal report and a final report for LAUC. Based on the outcomes of the program, we will also seek opportunities to share our results with our professional colleagues via a blog post to DH+Lib,¹⁵ conference presentations (e.g., DLF) as well as a publication.

Fall Quarter, 2017

Partner librarians and graduate student partners and assistants to present their projects to UCLA Library staff and invited colleagues. We will ask partner students and librarians as well as core library staff and our faculty advisor to reflect on the program: what worked well and where improvements could be made.

¹⁵ <http://acrl.ala.org/dh/>

SUMMER 2016 DRESSUP SCHEDULE

Boot Camp: July 28, 9am – 4pm.

Graduate student partners were asked to prepare 20-minute presentations of their research projects, followed by 10-minute discussions.

10-11am: Introductions/logistics, [overview](#) of the DResSUP program and staff.

11am-noon: Partner presentations.

Noon – 1pm: Lunch break.

1-1:30: Presentation by former DResSUP partner.

1:30-2:30: Partner presentations.

2:30–3: Planning of workshops/tutorials and topics.

Week One: Data collection, project management

8/1: Workshop: Web-scraping: [Import.io](#) (free, downloadable app). (Zoe Borovsky)

8/2: Workshop: [Web-indexing](#) with Python and Jupyter notebooks (free, downloadable app). (Peter Broadwell)

8/3: Reading: Best practices for data: metadata, file naming. (Claudia Horning)

Presentation: Text/data-mining: accessing library-licensed databases. (Angela Riggio)

8/4: Workshop: Digital Research Project Management. (Zoe Borovsky)

Week Two: Data cleaning, text mining/analysis

8/9: Workshop: Data cleaning: [OpenRefine](#) (free, downloadable app), regular expressions. (Dawn Childress)

8/10: Workshop: Text analysis: [Voyant](#) (web-based); Text Mining: [Mallet](#) (free, downloadable app). (Zoe Borovsky)

8/11: Presentation/Discussion: Data models. (Dawn Childress)

8/12: Presentation/Discussion: Storing, Sharing and Publishing Data. (Claudia Horning)

Week Three: Data analysis, visualization, publication

8/15: Presentation/Discussion: Data Visualization and Context. (Jonathan Crisman)

8/16: Workshop: Network Analysis: [Gephi](#) (free, downloadable app), [Cytoscape](#) (free, downloadable app) (Zoe Borovsky)

8/17: Workshop: Visualization with [Tableau Public](#) (free, downloadable app) (Andy Rutkowski)

Discussion: former DResSUP partner: (Nina Flores, Urban Planning)

8/18: Workshop: Storing, Sharing and Publishing Data II: GitHub (Dawn Childress)

Weeks Four and Five: Project work

Week Six: Wrap Up

Appendix B Student Assistant Job Description

UCLA

Library

Library Human Resources

Library Student Job Description

This job description form must be used for all student positions in the UCLA Library. Information should be typed into the form in the appropriate box or area. The form should be submitted to the Library Student Recruitment Coordinator in both print and electronic form – the electronic file should be submitted via e-mail and the print version should be submitted with all required signatures.

DO NOT COMPLETE TOP SECTION – OFFICIAL USE ONLY

1	Title Code	
2	Classification Sub	

3	Approved Payroll Title	
	Effective Date	
4	Act. Type	
5	ER/BU Code	
6	JA Number	
7	Exception	Yes OR No
8	Department Code	
9	Compensation Analyst/ Classification Reviewer & Date	
10	C Code	
11	Employment Representative & Date	
12	E Code	
13	Critical Position	Yes OR No
14	Conflict of Interest	Yes OR No

15	Reason for Position Description: <i>* The description must indicate which responsibilities were added or changed since last review.</i>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Position <input type="checkbox"/> Reclassification Requested* <input type="checkbox"/> Update/Review Requested* <input type="checkbox"/> Update for Record Only*
16	Name of Incumbent	
17	Department / Department Code	Collections, Research and Instruction/

18	Percentage of Time	100%
19	Type of Position	CASUAL/RESTRICTED
20	Present Payroll Title	_ Assistant II
21	Title Code	
22	ER/BU Code	/
23	Working Title (if Different)	
24	Requested Payroll Title	__ Assistant II
25	Requisition	(LHR Use Only)
26	Name of Supervisor	Zoe Borovsky
27	Payroll Title of Supervisor	Librarian
28	For LHR Use Only	
29	Name of Person Who Assigns Work (if different from 26)	Claudia Horning, Peter Broadwell
30	Payroll Title of Person Who Assigns Work	
31	Name of Department Head	Jennifer Osorio
32	Title of Department Head	Interim Head, Collections, Research and Instruction

Section 33 / Directly supervises the following employees:

Name of Employee	Job Title	FTE

Section 34 / List positions reporting directly to employees named in Section 33

Number of Employees	Job Title

Section 35 / Extent of supervisory responsibility for employees. [Indicate all that are applicable.]

Extent of Supervisory Responsibility	Indicate YES or NO
Final Selection	
Training	
Work Assignment	
Work Review	
Performance Appraisal	
Discipline	

Section 36 / List any licenses, certificates, degrees, or credentials that are required by law for the job.

N/A

Section 37 / List any machines, tools, equipment, office appliances, or motor vehicles which are required to do the job. Indicate whether use is occasional, frequent, or constant.

Equipment	Indicate if use is
	OCCASIONAL, FREQUENT, CONSTANT

Personal Computer	Constant
Printers	Frequent
Phone	Occasional
FAX	Occasional
Photocopier	Occasional
Typewriter	Never

Section 38 / Signatures [Signatures indicate neither agreement nor disagreement with classification requested.]

EMPLOYEE SIGNATURE

DATE

I certify that the information on this form is correct and complete and describes my job as I understand it.

DIRECT SUPERVISOR SIGNATURE

DATE

I have reviewed the statements on this form and certify to their accuracy.

DEPARTMENT HEAD SIGNATURE

DATE

I have reviewed the statements on this form and certify to their accuracy.

Section 39 / Summary Statement

Working in the Collections, Research, and Instruction Department on Digital projects, the Digital Project Assistant works as a member of the Digital Research Team to assist UCLA graduate students with initiating digital research projects and training them to continue the work. Incumbent helps 1) analyze clients' needs and skills to determine achievable scope and solutions, 2) establish workflows and best practices to collect, create, convert, edit, and review digital files--images, video, audio, text, 3) follow guidelines on creating metadata, 4) test the workflow by performing a preliminary analysis or visualization, i.e., spatial or textual, 5) document procedures and 6) train the graduate student researchers to work on their projects.

Section 40 / Type of Supervision Received/Exercised

The Digital Scholarship Librarian, Zoe Borovsky, schedules work, reviews quality and efficiency of work. Peter Broadwell (Digital Library) and Claudia Horning (Cataloging and Metadata) provide for training of the incumbent. Supervision is on site, but daily work is self-directed. New assignments are provided roughly every week on an as needed basis.

Section 41 / How long have the duties and distribution of time been substantially as below?

This is a new position.

Section 42 / Core Functions & Duties

Percentage of Time	Core Functions & Duties	Type of Function Essential OR Marginal
25%	A. Create/collect digital assets	
	A1. Follow procedures set out by Digital Library Programmer and/or Metadata Librarian	Essential

- | | | |
|-----|---|-----------|
| A2. | Collect/mine data from social media or other online resources (e.g. Hathi Trust) | Essential |
| A3. | Scan images of analog resources according to specifications provided | Essential |
| A4. | Digitize print material according to specifications provided using flatbed or large map scanner | Essential |
| A5. | Create digital audio files using WaveLab, Audacity, or similar sound-editing software. | Essential |
| A6. | Use care and follow handling instructions while working with rare and fragile materials | Essential |
| A7. | Prepare materials and work orders for delivery to SRLF digitization lab. | Essential |
| A8. | Keep track of work for tracking, statistical and management purposes | Essential |

	A9. Copy digital assets from one location to another	Essential
	A10. Use Adobe Photoshop to edit and review digital images	Essential
25%	B. Convert/format/describe digital assets	
	B1. Convert and clean data using Google Refine	Essential
	B2. Assign metadata to digital assets as needed	Essential
	B3. Understanding of metadata standards and controlled vocabulary	Essential
	B4. Transcribe foreign languages even when incumbent does not know the language	Essential
25%	C. Review existing metadata, create storage and access strategies	
	C1. Quality control, checking others work, fixing errors	Essential
	C2. Review metadata in XML	Essential

		Outline data storage strategies and access methods using available web/cloud services	
25%	D.	Test workflow, perform analysis, document procedure	
	D1.	Test workflow by uploading digital file or files and performing an analysis, display, or visualization	Essential
	D2.	Adjust workflow as needed and document procedures	Essential
	D3.	Train clients to follow procedures to perform additional work	Essential

Importance	Duty
Section 43 / Competencies [SKAs, Behaviors, Attributes]	Reference
Preferred,	(Required,
Trained)	May be

- | | | | |
|----|---|-----|----------|
| 1. | Ability to get to work reliably and on time. | All | Required |
| 2. | Ability to be present in the workplace during normal working hours. | All | Required |

3.	Ability to initiate and maintain cooperative working relationships with co-workers, supervisors, and managers.	All	Required
4.	Ability to work with co-workers, supervisors, and managers harmoniously and cooperatively and as a team player.	All	Required
5.	Ability to follow directions from supervisors.	All	Required
6.	Attention to detail.	All	Required
7.	Experienced in using personal computer and web applications.	All	Required
8.	Experience using Microsoft Word, Excel, Access.	All	Required
9.	Experience using Adobe Photoshop.	B	Preferred
10.	Experience using WaveLab, Audacity, or similar sound-editing software.	B	May be Trained
11.	Experience using, creating and editing XML and KML.	C	May be Trained
13.	Experience using ArcGIS, Google Earth, and web-based mapping applications.	?	Preferred
14.	Experience using Google Sheets, Docs and Refine.		Preferred
15.	Ability to learn new software applications.		Required
16.	Working knowledge of basic web technologies, including HTML and standard file formats.		Required

17. Ability to convey technical knowledge to beginning computer users in one-on-one and group situations and through written documentation. Required
18. Familiarity with institutionally supported document storage and management services (e.g., Google Apps for Education, Box). Required
19. Familiarity with JavaScript and database queries (SQL)
Preferred

Appendix C Detailed Timetable

Winter Quarter, 2017	Core Library Staff	Partner Librarians	Graduate Student Assistant (LAUC-funded)
Week 1: Jan 9	Hire the graduate student assistant	4 hrs. per week release time for 10 weeks. Begin working with MacBook Pro Laptops	Begins working part-time (20 hrs. per week) in the SIL
Week 2: Jan 16	Introduction to DResSUP for Partner Librarians and graduate student assistant.	Write self-assessments	Preparation for DResSUP program
Week 3: Jan 23	2-2 hour sessions per week for 8 weeks (Weeks 3-10): 1. Overview 2. Office hours: facilitating hands-on project work w/partners	1. Attend workshop series (Overview): 1 hr. 1. Facilitated project work w/core staff: 1 hr. 2. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week to facilitate work of Partner Librarians.

Week 4: Jan 30	Hold 1. Workshop series: Collection 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Attend workshop series, Collection: 1hr 2. Facilitated project work: 1hr 3. Team project work: 2hrs	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 5: Feb 6	1. Cleaning 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Cleaning: 1hrs 2. Facilitated project work: 1hrs 3. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 6: Feb 13	1. Analysis, Visualization 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Analysis, Visualization: 1hr 2. Facilitated project work 1hrs 3. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 7: Feb 20	1. Sharing, Publication 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Sharing, Publication: 1hr 2. Facilitated project work: 1 hr. 3. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 8: Feb 27	1. Write letter of intent for IMLS grant 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Facilitated project work 2 hrs. 2. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 9: Mar 6	1. Hold text/data mining joint session 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Attend text/data mining joint session 1 hr. 2. Facilitated project work: 1 hr. 3. Team project work 2 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week
Week 10: Mar 13- Mar 17	1. Office hours w/partners	1. Facilitated project work 1 hr. 2. Team project work: 3 hrs.	Available in the SIL for 20 hours per week

Spring Quarter, 2017	Core Library Staff	Partner Librarians	Graduate Student Assistant (LAUC funded)
Week 1: Apr	Issue call for DResSUP	Release time: 8 hrs. per week	Works 20 hours per week in

3	graduate student partners (deadline: June 10 with notification of acceptance, June 16)	for 9 weeks; 20 hrs. during Week 8. 1. Review workshop materials for weeks 4-7: 4 hrs. 2. Team project work: 4 hrs.	the SIL, dividing time between 1) assisting Partner Librarians with their team project work, and 2) assisting with workshops.
Week 2: Apr 10	Promote workshop series, targeting graduate students	1. Revise workshop materials: 4 hrs. 2. Team project work: 4 hrs.	Continues as above
Week 3: Apr 17	2-2 hour sessions per week for 8 weeks: 1. Introduction to DResSUP (featuring a previous grad student partner) 2. Office hours: facilitating hands-on project work w/partners	1. Create new workshop materials: 4 hrs. 2. Facilitated project work w/core staff: 2 hrs. 3. Team project work: 2 hrs.	Cont.
Week 4: Apr 24	Hold workshop series 1. Collection 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Plan, assist, and assess workshops: 2 hrs. 2. Debrief and facilitated project work: 1 hrs. 3. Team project work: 5 hrs.	Cont.
Week 5: May 1	1. Cleaning 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Plan, assist, and assess workshops: 2 hrs. 2. Debrief and facilitated project work: 1 hrs. 3. Team project work: 5 hrs.	Cont.
Week 6: May 8	1. Analysis, Visualization 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Plan, assist, and assess workshops: 2 hrs. 2. Debrief and participate in facilitated project work: 1 hrs. 3. Team project work: 5 hrs.	Cont.

Week 7: May 15	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sharing, Publication 2. Office hours w/partners 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plan, assist, and assess workshops: 2 hrs. 2. Debrief and participate in facilitated project work: 1 hrs. 3. Team project work: 5 hrs. 	Cont.
Week 8: May 22	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hold daily (1 hr.) office hours with partners 	<p>Half-time (50%) release time for 40 hours project planning for Summer:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 10 hrs. research (tools and content, including background), 2. 10 hrs. project planning. 	Cont.
Week 9: May 29	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recruit and interview for 2 grad student assistant positions 2. Assign leads and co-leads for DResSUP Summer workshops. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participate in grad student assistant interviews: 1 hr. 2. Assist with revising and planning DResSUP summer: 2 hrs. 3. Team project work 5 hrs. 	Cont.
Week 10: Jun 5- Jun 9	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Draft IMLS grant application (due Sept 2017) 2. Prepare LAUC status report (due April 14, 2017) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assist with drafting IMLS grant application: 2 hrs. 2. Assist with preparing LAUC status report: 2 hrs. 3. Team project work: 4 hrs. 	Cont.

Summer Session, 2017	Core Library Staff	Partner Librarians	Graduate Student Assistant (UCLA funded)
Jun 12-26	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Review grad student partner applications 2. Send acceptance letters: Jun 16 3. Hire graduate 		

	student assistant: Jun 26		
Week 1: Jul 17	DResSUP begins. Core staff leads workshops (Weeks 1-3) 1. Boot Camp Jul 17: Introduction to DResSUP 2. Workshop series: Collection	Half-time release (20 hrs. per week) begins Jul 17, ends Sept 1. 1. Co-lead and assess workshops: 5 hrs. 2. Project work: 15 hrs.	Works full-time 40 hrs. per week for 7 weeks.
Week 2: Jul 24	1. Data Cleaning 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Co-lead and assess workshops: 5 hrs. 2. Project work: 15 hrs.	Continues as above
Week 3: Jul 31	1. Analysis, Visualization 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Co-lead and assess workshops: 5 hrs. 2. Project work: 15 hrs.	Cont.
Week 4: Aug 7	1. Sharing, Publication 2. Office hours w/partners	1. Co-lead and assess workshops: 5 hrs. 2. Project work: 15 hrs.	Cont.
Week 5: Aug 14	1. Office hours w/partners	1. Project work: 20 hrs.	Cont.
Week 6: Aug 21	1. Office hours w/partners	1. Project work: 20 hrs.	Cont.
Week 7: Aug 28	1. Review assessment of both grad student and librarian partners 2. Prepare an internal report, 3. Plan Fall Presentation	1. Program assessment: 10 hrs. 2. Project work focus on presentation: 10 hrs.	Cont.

Fall Quarter, 2017	Core Library Staff	Partner Librarians
Oct 2 – Oct 20	Prepare and host Fall Presentation	
Oct 23 - 31	Wrap up, debrief, and prepare final report for LAUC	

Appendix D Letter of Support

(page 33)

October 27, 2016

11334 Charles E. Young Research Library
Box 951575
Los Angeles, CA 90095-1575

Dear LAUC,

I am writing to express my enthusiastic support for this LAUC research grant proposal. The proposal outlines what promises to be an innovative and scalable approach to training librarians in the skills and methods they need to support advanced digital research. The proposal carefully outlines a pedagogical approach, giving guidance and opportunities for both hands-on training and skill-building and immediate application by participating in library/researcher partnerships.

Over the past two years, I have provided support for the DResSUP initiative, watching librarians connect with graduate students to build a community of practice in our Research Commons, which serves as their “home base” during the six-week summer program. The graduate students come out of the experience with new expertise and a profound respect for the library’s collections and staff members. We view this program as a critical investment in and innovative model for solving issues and demands that are not specific to UCLA but ones that definitely meet the needs of our research communities. Through this process we have identified gaps in our services that DResSUP fulfills; the challenge remaining is to build capacity in a way that will be sustainable so that the library can become an equal partner in the full research life-cycle.

This LAUC grant is designed to address capacity-building issues that are part of ongoing discussions in the larger library profession, with programs emerging at Columbia and other institutions. To my knowledge, *DResSUP for Librarians* poses an innovative solution by integrating the continuing education track alongside the ongoing and successful graduate training program. The budget reflects UCLA Library’s commitment to continuing education and professional development of our staff; I recognize the need for release time and equipment to support this program. However LAUC support will supply critical high-level graduate student assistance during the six-week project-based learning aspect of their program: building an online interactive digital project focused on the LA Times Photographic Archive.

I look forward to the planned library presentation and written reports assessing the efficacy of the program by participants. Past presentations about DResSUP for library managers and subject librarians led to discussion where librarians indicated enthusiasm for opportunities to participate in DResSUP as a way to develop their digital research skill-set and capacities. We hope to build upon that momentum and I would welcome LAUC as a partner in supporting this initiative as a way of underscoring the importance of librarians developing research skills that allow them to be active participants in the research process.

Sincerely,

Virginia Steel
University Librarian

Zoe Borovsky

A1540 Charles E. Young Research Library
310 825 4954
zoe@library.ucla.edu

EDUCATION

University of California, Berkeley, CA Ph.D. in Scandinavian Languages and Literatures Dissertation: "Rocking the Boat: Women in Old Norse Literature"	1994
University of Wisconsin, Madison, WI M.A. in Scandinavian	1988
University of Wisconsin, Madison, WI B.A. with Distinction in Scandinavian Honors: Phi Beta Kappa (1986)	1986

TEACHING EXPERIENCE

University of California, Los Angeles, CA Adjunct Assistant Professor – "Introduction to Scandinavian Literature and Culture." Developed syllabus and overall course structure, incorporated new instructional technologies, supervised and trained TAs, and administered all grades.	2004
University of Oregon, Eugene, OR Assistant Professor of Norwegian Developed a four-year curriculum for undergraduates studying Norwegian language and Scandinavian literature, advised students with majors in Germanic with minor in Scandinavian.	1994-1999

RELATED EXPERIENCE

Charles E. Young Research Library, University of California, Los Angeles, CA Librarian for Digital Research and Scholarship	2011 - present
Institute for Digital Research and Education, University of California, Los Angeles, CA Digital Humanities Research Consultant Consult and implement technical solutions, provide support from grant-writing from conceptual design to technical specifications, and manage grant-supported projects and staff.	2007 - 2011
Center for Digital Humanities, University of California, Los Angeles, CA Associate Head: UDHIG Assisted Faculty Head by initiating a new unit dedicated to supporting innovative research projects by coordinating with other technical units at UCLA, developing grant proposals and supervising a dedicated programmer.	2005 - 2007
Academic Services Manager Supervised a team of seven full-time programmers, web developers,	2002-2005

designers and seven part-time graduate student technologists to assist humanities faculty in the use of technology, i.e., development of courseware and course web-sites, oversaw a budget of over \$1 million annually.

2Bridge Software, San Francisco, CA
Director of Training and Documentation

2000-2002

Produced technical documents and training for developers, administrators, and end-users of a web-based publishing and content management system (2Share). Hired, supervised, and trained a team of technical writers and trainers.

PUBLICATIONS

In Print

- Borovsky, Zoe, and Elizabeth McAulay. 2015. "Digital Humanities Curriculum Support inside the Library." In *Digital Humanities in the Library: Challenges and Opportunities for Subject Specialists*. Eds. A. Hartsell-Gundy, L. Braunstein, and L. Golomb.
- Chen, Jack W., Zoe Borovsky, Yoh Kawano, and Ryan Chen. "The Shishuo Xinyu as Data Visualization." *Early Medieval China* 20, 2014.
- Birnbaum, David J., Zoe Borovsky, James Danowski, and Cynthia M. Vakareliyska. "Orthodox Saints as Facebook Friends: Social Networking and Medieval Manuscripts." In *Horace Lunt Memorial Volume. Slavica*. Bloomington, IN. 2013
- "Transformation Begins When the Renovation is Done: Reconfiguring Staff and Services to Meet 21st-Century Research Needs," In *Imagine, Innovate, Inspire: Proceedings of the ACRL 2013 Conference*, edited by Association of College and Research Libraries and Mueller, Dawn M National Conference. Chicago: Association of College and Research Libraries.
- "Never in Public: Women and Performance in Old Norse Texts," *Journal of American Folklore*, Winter, (1999), pp. 6-39.
- "Sagas of Icelanders" in *Medieval Folklore: An Encyclopedia of Myths, Legends, Tales, Beliefs, and Customs*. Eds. C. Lindahl, J. McNamara, and J. Lindow. ABC-Clio, 2000, pp. 849-854.
- "'En hon er blandin mjök' Women and Insults in Old-Norse/Icelandic Literature," in *Cold Counsel: The Women of Old Norse Literature and Myth*. Eds. K. Swenson and S. M. Anderson. Garland, 1999, pp. 1-14.

LANGUAGES

- English – native language
- Norwegian – speak fluently and read/write with high proficiency
- Old Norse/Icelandic, Danish and Swedish – read with high proficiency.

RELATED SKILLS

Conceptual knowledge of web development, databases, XML, XSLT, and development environments: PHP and Java. Fluency with XML text-markup standards (TEI). Familiarity with spatial analysis tools (GIS) and standards (KML). Advanced knowledge of applications developed for text encoding, text-analysis, network-analysis and visualization. Working knowledge of standard computer office applications.

Curriculum Vitae of Peter M. Broadwell

22484 Charles E. Young Research Library
Los Angeles, CA 90095-1575

broadwell@library.ucla.edu
310-825-6158

As the Academic Projects Developer in the UCLA Digital Library, I work with faculty, library specialists, and students to develop novel online resources that use emerging technologies in computational analysis, digital archiving, and multimedia presentation to support collaborative scholarship in the humanities and social sciences.

Degrees Received

- Ph.D. in Musicology from UCLA, December 2010
- M.A. in Musicology from UCLA, June 2006
- M.S. in Computer Science from UC Berkeley, May 2004
- B.A. with honors in Computer Science from Grinnell College, May 2001

Academic Research

September 2015 - Present

Academic Projects Developer, Digital Library Program, UCLA Library

September 2011 - August 2014

Council on Library and Information Resources Postdoctoral Fellow, Digital Initiatives and Information Technology, UCLA Library

October 2010 - August 2011

Research Fellow, Danish Folklore Project, Scandinavian Section, UCLA

April 2008 - October 2010

Graduate Student Researcher, Danish Folklore Project, Scandinavian Section, UCLA

Projects Developed

- **The UCLA NewsScape** and **NewsSCOPE**: a massive, searchable online archive of television news videos and interactive summary visualizations
- **WitchHunter** and **GhostScope**: experimental interfaces for visualizing conceptual geographies in a very large collection of nineteenth-century Danish folklore
- **Topics in the Quan Tang shi**: a browser for exploring the distributions of latent topics in a collection of 35,000 classical Chinese poems
- **The Danish Folklore Nexus**: an interface for the study of a curated corpus of Danish folklore, incorporating geographic, topical, historical, and biographical perspectives

Refereed Publications

- **WitchHunter: Tools for the Geo-Semantic Exploration of a Danish Folklore Corpus**
T. Tangherlini, P. Broadwell. *Journal of American Folklore* 511 (Winter 2016), 14-42.
- **Comparing Published Scientific Journal Articles to Their Pre-print Versions**
M. Klein, P. Broadwell, S. Farb and T. Grappone. *Proceedings of the Joint Council on Digital Libraries 2016*, Rutgers University, June 2016.
- **Semi-Supervised Morphosyntactic Classification of Old Icelandic**
K. Urban, T. Tangherlini, A. Vijunas, P. Broadwell. *PLOS ONE*, published July 16, 2014.
- **Sites of (re)Collection: Creating the Danish Folklore Nexus**
T. Tangherlini, P. Broadwell. *Journal of Folklore Research* 51:2 (2014), 223-247.
- **TrollFinder: Geo-Semantic Exploration of a Very Large Corpus of Danish Folklore**
P. Broadwell, T. Tangherlini. *Proceedings of the Workshop on Computational Models of Narrative*, Istanbul, Turkey, May 29, 2012.
- **The Trouble with House Elves: Computational Folkloristics and Classification**
J. Abello, P. Broadwell, T. Tangherlini. *Communications of the ACM* 55:7 (July 2012), 60-70.

Academic Teaching

April - June 2013, April - June 2015

Technical advisor for DH 199/299 – capstone seminar for Digital Humanities undergraduate and graduate students; oversaw projects involving automated comparison of responses to news events on social media and television news

June - August 2007

Summer Course Instructor, Department of Musicology, UCLA
Music History 135B – History of Opera: Romantic Period

Technical Skills

- **Geographic information systems:** ArcMap, Google Earth, Google Maps, OpenLayers
- **Linguistic and statistical analysis:** OpenCalais, Stanford NLP, KNIME, R
- **Social network analysis:** Gephi, Cytoscape, GraphView
- **Server administration:** Linux, Windows 7-8, networks and virtual machines
- **Archive management:** Islandora, Apache Solr, MySQL, PostgreSQL
- **Web interfaces:** Drupal and Joomla CMS, Adobe Flex, HTML, JavaScript/AJAX, jQuery
- **Programming languages:** PHP, Python, Perl, shell scripting, Java, C, C++

Other Activities

- Conference organizer for *Dodging the Memory Hole 2016: Saving Online News*, October 13-14, 2016, UCLA
- Participant in the Culture Analytics Long Program, UCLA Institute for Pure and Applied Mathematics (IPAM), March - June 2016
- Project mentor, Google Summer of Code, June - August 2015

- Academic mentor of the Shoah Foundation Institute project team, UCLA Institute for Pure and Applied Mathematics (IPAM) Research in Industrial Projects for Students summer program, June - August 2011
- Technical editor and web designer for *Echo: A Music-Centered Journal*, an interdisciplinary, peer-reviewed online journal created and edited by the students of the UCLA Department of Musicology [echo.ucla.edu], 2005 - 2010

DAWN CHILDRESS

POSITIONS HELD

Librarian, Digital Collections & Scholarship, Digital Library Program, UCLA, September 2015-present

Sally W. Kalin Librarian for Technological Innovation and Humanities Librarian, Arts & Humanities Library, Penn State University Libraries-University Park. October 2008-August 2015

Visiting Librarian for Germanic Studies, French & Italian, Comparative Literature, and Linguistics, Indiana University Libraries-Bloomington. January 2006-October 2008

EDUCATION

MLS Rare Books and Manuscripts, concentrations in book history and digital Libraries, Indiana University-Bloomington, December 2007

Graduate coursework in German Language and Literature, Eberhard-Karls-Universität, Tübingen, Germany, 2001/2002

BA in Germanic Languages and Literature; Philosophy, *cum laude*, Washington University in St. Louis, August 2001

RECENT AWARDS, HONORS, AND GRANTS

Center for Humanities and Information (CHI) Grant, for *Translating Networks: Exploring Literary Translation Communities Through Graph Theory*, with Thomas O. Beebee, 2016-2017.

University Libraries Innovation Micro-grant, Penn State Libraries, for *Experiments in Literary Cartography: Mapping 19th c. Paris in Literature*, 2014-2015.

University Libraries Grant, Penn State Libraries, for *Better OCR with Tesseract*, 2014-2015.

Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence (SITE) Grant, for *Mapping Matters: Space and Place in the Humanities*, with Prof. Willa Silverman, 2014-2015.

University Libraries Innovation Micro-grant, Penn State Libraries, for *The Open Bibliography Project*, 2013-2014.

Sally W. Kalin Librarianship for Technological Innovation, endowed appointment, 2012-2015.

MLA International Bibliography Fellowship, 2011-2015.

RECENT BOOKS, ARTICLES, PAPERS (SELECTED)

Childress, Dawn. "Critical Catalogue Considerations," DH 2017, with Molly Hardy and Paige Morgan, submitted.

Childress, Dawn. "Editorial Matters: Data, Truth, and Interpretation in the Archives," The Digital Antiquarian Conference, American Antiquarian Society, May 2015. <http://dawnchildress.com/2015/06/02/editorial-matters/>

Childress, Dawn and Daniel Hickey. "Liaison Librarians and Scholarly Communication: A Framework and Strategies for Assessment," in *Assessing Liaison Librarians: Documenting Impact for Positive Change*. Mack, Daniel C. and Gary White, eds. Chicago: PIL, 2014.

Childress, Dawn. "The Local Digital Humanities Landscape: Understanding and Building Community, Capacity, and Infrastructure," Bibliothekartag 2013, Leipzig, Germany (March 2013)

RECENT CONFERENCES AND PRESENTATIONS (SELECTED)

“Minimal Computing in Libraries: Case Studies and the Case for” DLF 2016, Milwaukee, November 2016.

“Managing Scope and Scale: Applying the Incubator Model to Digital Scholarship” DLF 2016, Milwaukee, November 2016.

“Translating Networks: Exploring Literary Translation Communities Through Graph Theory” SHARP 2016, Paris, France, July 2016. <https://dawnchildress.com/2016/08/13/sharp16/>

“Building Capacity with Care: A Workshop” Digital Humanities 2016, Kraków, Poland, July 2016. <http://dhgradlabor.github.io/dh2016workshop/>

“Alternative Infrastructures for Digital Projects,” with Andy Rutkowski, DH Infrastructure Symposium, Los Angeles, CA, February 2016. <http://dawnchildress.com/2016/02/27/dhinfrastucture/>

Organizer and Panel Co-chair with David Oberhelman, “The Evolving Scholarly Record,” MLA Convention, Austin, TX, January 2016. <https://mlabib.commons.mla.org/mla-2016-the-evolving-scholarly-record/>

Co-organizer, *Mapping Matters: Space and Place in the Humanities Classroom*, with Prof. Will Silverman and Carl Cornell, Penn State University, April 2015. <http://sites.psu.edu/litmaps/>

Organizer and Panel Chair, “Bibliography for the 21st Century,” MLA Annual Convention, Vancouver, B.C., January 2015. <http://mlalibraries.commons.mla.org/mla-programming/2015-bibliography-for-the-21st-century/>

“Network Analysis of Literary Translation in the U.S.,” with Prof. Thomas Beebee, Liberal Arts Scholarship and Technology Summit, Penn State University, September 2014. <https://speakerdeck.com/kirschbombe/network-analysis-of-literary-translation-in-the-u-dot-s>

DIGITAL INITIATIVES & PROJECTS (SELECTED)

Translating Networks: Analysis and Visualization of Contemporary Literary Translation, with Prof. Thomas Beebee (co-PI), 2014-present.

A Framework for Digital Travel Diaries: TEI/RDF framework to facilitate researcher participation in digital text collections, 2015-present.

Experiments in Literary Cartography: Belle Epoque Paris, with Prof. Willa Silverman (co-PI), expansion on the earlier project “Mapping Maupassant’s *Bel-Ami*” (<https://humanitieslab.psu.edu/projects/mappingbelami/>), 2013-2015.

Magasin des demoiselles, with Prof. Benedicte Monicat (co-PI), a multi-component project consisting of a digital edition, text analysis (stylistics, topic modeling), and digital humanities pedagogy, 2014-2015.

Humanities {Lab}, experimental environment to support collaborative digital humanities research and pedagogy projects, 2013-2015. <https://humanitieslab.psu.edu>

Les Écrits de Aimé Césaire: bibliographie commentée (1913-2008): an annotated bibliography and research portal to the works of Francophone poet and activist, Aimé Césaire, with Prof. Thomas Hale and Kora Véron (co-PIs), 2012-2015. <http://lesecritscesaire.libraries.psu.edu>

TECHNICAL

Web & Standards: Git, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, GeoJSON, TEI, Dublin Core, MODS, EAD

Content Management & Databases: Omeka/Neatline, Wordpress, Juxta, Versioning Machine, OJS, Islandora, Collective Access, XTE, MySQL, Exist

Analysis: Gephi, R Studio,

Currently learning: XSLT/XQuery, Python, Ruby/Rails, Tesseract

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EDUCATION

<i>UCLA</i> Master of Library and Information Science	2012
<i>UCLA</i> Bachelor of Arts, History	1991

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

<i>UCLA Library Cataloging & Metadata Center</i> Director, Metadata Services	2014-
Serve as the Library's principal metadata librarian and director of metadata services. Provide expert leadership and guidance in the selection of schemas, thesauri, and data design for digital initiatives in the Library; plan, manage, and review metadata for digital projects; act as a liaison both within and outside of the Library on questions relating to digital initiatives; supervise members of the Cataloging & Metadata Center's Metadata Team, and provide oversight of all cataloging and metadata for digital resources and monographs; and serve as a contact for metadata consultations by UCLA faculty and staff.	
<i>UCLA Library Cataloging & Metadata Center</i> Head, Metadata Team	2011-2014
<i>UCLA Library Cataloging & Metadata Center</i> Head, Digital Resources Metadata Section	2009-2011
<i>UCLA Library Cataloging & Metadata Center</i> E-Resources Specialist	2006-2009
<i>UCLA Library Cataloging & Metadata Center</i> Open Sets Cataloger	2001-2009
<i>UCLA Library Cataloging Department</i> SRLF Transfer Coordinator & Added Volumes/Locations Processor	1991-2001

PUBLICATIONS & PRESENTATIONS

Borovsky, Z., Broadwell, P., Crisman, J., Horning, C., Klein, M., & Liang, Y. (February 2016). "Digital Research StartUp Partnerships with the UCLA Library." Presentation at the Digital Humanities Infrastructure Symposium, Los Angeles, CA.

Briston, H., Cuellar, J., Horning, C. & Loera, A. (May 2016). "So many things are possible when you don't know they're impossible: Building Collaborative Tools & Workflows for Digitization." Presentation at the Digital Initiatives Symposium, San Diego, CA.

- Davison, S. & Horning, C. (April 2012). *Linked Data and the Semantic Web*. Lightning talk on linked data, RDF, schema.org, and the semantic Web at the UCLA Digital Library Showcase at UCLA Library, Los Angeles, CA.
- Davison, S., McAulay, E., & Horning, C. (November 2013). "Enhancing an OAI-PMH Service Using Linked Data." Presentation at the Digital Library Federation (DLF) Forum, Austin, TX.
- Davison, S., Sugiyama, Y., McAulay, E., & Horning, C. (2013). "Enhancing an OAI-PMH Service Using Linked Data: A Report from the Sheet Music Consortium." *Journal of Library Metadata* 13 (2-3), 141-162. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/19386389.2013.826067>
- Horning, C. (2016). "Handbook of Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies." *Cataloging & Classification Quarterly*, 54(7), pp. 504–505. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01639374.2016.1216911>
- Horning, C. (November 2012). *Innovators and Advocates: Celebrating California's Library Hall of Fame Librarians*. Presentation on Miriam Matthews at the California Library Association Conference, San Jose, CA.
- Horning, C. M. (2012). *Trailblazing librarian in the golden state: A look at the life and career of Miriam Matthews*. (University of California, Los Angeles). *ProQuest Dissertations and Theses*. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1267138451?accountid=14512>
- Davison, S., McAulay, E., & Horning, C. (November 2013). "Enhancing an OAI-PMH Service Using Linked Data." Presentation at the Digital Library Federation (DLF) Forum, Austin, TX.
- Starr, J., Willett, P., Federer, L., Horning, C., & Bergstrom, M. L. (2012). "A Collaborative Framework for Data Management Services: The Experience of the University of California." *Journal of eScience Librarianship* 1(2): Article 7. <http://dx.doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.2012.1014>

PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES & MEMBERSHIPS

American Library Association (ALA), *Member*, 2008-

California Library Association (CLA), *Member*, 2009-

Library of Congress. Program for Cooperative Cataloging Provider-Neutral E-Monograph Record Task Group, *Member*, 2008-2009

OCLC Research Library Partnership Web Archiving Metadata Working Group, *Member*, 2016-

Andrzej Rutkowski

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EDUCATION

MLS, *Library and Information Science* Palmer School Long Island University, 2013

MA, *John W. Draper Program in Humanities and Social Thought*, New York University, 2005

BA, *Philosophy, with minors in Film and Sociology*, University of Vermont, 2001

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Geospatial Resources Librarian **June 2014 - present**

Charles E. Young Research Library, University of California Los Angeles

Develop and support a wide range of geospatial resources and services for the UCLA academic community, including direct research support to students, faculty, and staff.

Interdisciplinary GIS Library Fellow (2 year position) **September 2013 – June 2014**

Von Kleinsmid Center Library for International and Public Affairs, University of Southern California

Responsible for developing and supporting GIS related services and resources for the USC academic community.

Reference Associate for Business and Government Documents **Nov. 2005 - August 2013**

Bobst Library Research Commons, New York University

Provided reference and instructional support to the NYU community across a range of disciplines and methods.

RECENT PRESENTATIONS and WORKSHOPS

"Mapping LA's Murals," *California Map Society Fall 2016 Southern California Meeting*, Fullerton, CA. October 22, 2016.

"Making Sense of Data through Visualization," *American Library Association Annual Meeting Preconference Workshop*, Orlando, FL. June 23rd, 2016.

"Map the Data, See the Data," *International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST)*, Bergen, NO. June 2nd, 2016.

"Mapping Collections, Making Connections," with Stacy Williams, *Art Libraries Society of North America (ARLIS)*, Seattle, WA. March 9th, 2016.

"Alternative Infrastructures for Digital Projects," with Dawn Childress, *DH Infrastructure Symposium*, Los Angeles, CA. February 27th, 2016.

GRANTS

University of Southern California Research Grant, 2014

\$2250 grant for "Mapping the ONE Archives" an online map application that will plot the location of gay bars and other establishments from historical Damron Address Books.

University of Southern California Dean's Challenge Grant Recipient, 2013-2014

\$1000 grant for "Spatially Speaking: A salon for GIS and spatial research.

New York University Green Grant recipient for the Green Map Project 2008-2009

\$5,000 grant used for initial creation, promotion, and outreach of Green Map System's "Green Map Archive."

RELEVANT SKILLS

- Proficient using ArcGIS, QGIS, ArcGIS.com, Google Fusion Tables, Carto, Tableau
- Knowledgeable in basic HTML, Python, CSS, Javascript, GeoJson
- Basic understanding of statistical software, including SPSS, SAS, STATA, ATLASi